

Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement

Deliverable 4.1

Biosecurity Measures Plan

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1 Introduction

Biosecurity is considered as an integrated part of restoration practice through the project and will be addressed by the adoption of this specific biosecurity measures plan (BMP, D4.1), fully compliant with the European guidelines on biosecurity in native oyster restoration (zu Ermgassen et al. 2020). This plan will go far beyond the legislative obligations (Figure 1) and will include the code of practice to prevent any biological risks and means of verification, including genetic analyses. The BMP will consider three main aspects:

1. preventing and monitoring oyster diseases,
2. preventing and monitoring non-indigenous species invasion,
3. ensuring and monitoring oyster and sabellariid polychaetes population genetic diversity and connectivity to other populations.

Figure 1. Legislation and policy on biosecurity at a variety of scales (adapted from Oidtmann et al. 2011).

The BMP will contain all the measures to be taken to mitigate and contrast adverse events. The BMP will also contain an analysis of the risks and feasibility of possible interventions and countermeasures, taking into consideration the respective costs / benefits.

Annual BRs implementation and biosecurity reports will be provided (D4.3, D4.4, D4.5).

The project **LIFE NatuReef** has been co-financed by the Programme LIFE 2021-2027

1.1 Importance of biosecurity in native oysters' restoration

The development and implementation of biosecurity strategies are vital to minimise disease risks by reducing the likelihood of pathogen introduction and the potential consequences. Such strategies also aim to prevent the establishment of pathogens in the wild where they could have serious impacts on wild aquatic animal populations and act as a reservoir of infection for farmed animal populations.

The reintroduced of native oysters are likely to be able to cope with new pathogen and stresses encountered at the destination site; however, the project has specific task to ensure the biosecurity and avoid the risk of reintroducing new pathogens in the destination area will be minimised (Preston et al. 2020).

Biosecurity plan involves practices, procedures and policies that are used to prevent the introduction and spread of pathogens and invasive species (Gunn et al. 2008). The principal steps in the development of biosecurity strategies are hazard identification, followed by a risk assessment process. Based on this knowledge, risk mitigation (prevention of introduction), disease detection and control (if introduction does take place) and eradication plans can be developed. These elements will vary depending on the level at which biosecurity strategies are applied.

Native oyster supply is a key limiting step in oyster restoration projects (Preston et al. 2020). Sourcing oysters from outside the local area can present significant biosecurity risks, which are time consuming and costly to address and impossible to eliminate completely. This is why our main supply of oysters will be local or regional wild stocks (broodstock, mean individual size 5 cm). Local stock may have adaptations suited for survival in the area and existing genetic structure in the population is maintained, ensuring genetic diversity. However, when considering using wild stocks, the impact on the donor site must be considered first. Indeed, the use of wild stocks to supply the demand from restoration has the potential to further damage the remaining populations. In this case, being a first demonstration restoration project in the area, the use of wild stock, already exploited to feed aquaculture plants, represents a good option and the project will ensure that the stock selection process is conducted responsibly and in accordance with legislation and biosecurity protocols. In addition, when needed, oysters will be kept alive in aquaculture facilities at the Ravenna harbour pending sowing on the BLR.

EU funded projects dealing with oyster restoration and related biosecurity issues, relevant for the present **LIFE NatuReef** project are:

- **HERPISH** Herpes virus in Irish oysters and identification of resistant stocks; ID: 327932; From: 1 June 2013 to: 31 May 2015; Coordinated in: Ireland; Programme: FP7-PEOPLE
- **BIVALIFE** Controlling infectious diseases in oysters and mussels in Europe; ID: 266157; From: 1 February 2011 to: 31 January 2014; Coordinated in: France; Programme: FP7-KBBE
- **LARVDEVOPTI** "Larval quality in oyster hatcheries: Effects of ocean acidification, temperature change and food availability on reproductive success and survival of the European flat oyster"; ID: 273851; From: 16 August 2011 to: 15 August 2013; Coordinated in: Sweden; Programme: FP7-PEOPLE
- **OYSTERECOVER** Establishing the scientific bases and technical procedures and standards to recover the European flat oyster production through strategies to tackle the main constraint, bonamiosis; ID: 243583; From: 1 May 2010 to: 31 October 2013; Coordinated in: Spain; Programme: FP7-SME
- **VIVALDI** Preventing and mitigating farmed bivalve diseases; ID: 678589; From: 1 March 2016 to: 29 February 2020; Coordinated in: France; Programme: H2020-EU.3.2.
- **REPROSEED** REsearch to improve PROduction of SEED of established and emerging bivalve species in European hatcheries; ID: 245119; Programme: FP7-KBBE
- **BOLCI(R)** Bonamia ostrae life cycle investigations, optimised production of resistant *Ostrea edulis* Spat, and studies of oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) immune mechanisms; ID: Q5CR-2002-72338; From: 1 April 2003 to: 30 September 2005; Coordinated in: Ireland; Programme: FP5-LIFE QUALITY

We will benefit from the knowledge gained from these projects in terms of resistance of populations to environmental conditions and pathogens (HERPISH, BIVALIFE, VIVALDI), and life cycle and reproduction (LARVDEVOPTI, OYSTERECOVER, REPROSEED, BOLCI(R)).

2 Permitting request

Since no shellfish reef restoration has been undertaken in the area considered, LIFE NatuReef will follow permitting processes related to other activities such as aquaculture, fisheries, biosecurity or marine construction. Based on Jeffs et al. (2019), the permitting processes will start in conjunction with the permits for the construction of the basal limestone reef and will be based on regular and frequent communication with the Regional and national entities involved in the requests. Moreover, relevant stakeholders have been already informed during the presentation of the project, starting from the kick-off meeting, and will be routinely involved during the different processes of the project. Finally, help from experienced shellfish restoration networks will be asked if needed (e.g., Native Oyster Restoration Alliance (NORA), <https://nora-europe.eu/>).

At the International level, LIFE NatuReef will follow the Regulation (EU) 1143/2014 on invasive alien species (the IAS Regulation) entered into force on 1 January 2015, fulfilling Action 16 of Target 5 of the EU 2020 Biodiversity Strategy, as well as Aichi Target 9 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020 under the Convention of Biological Diversity.

At the national level, LIFE NatuReef will follow the Decreto Legislativo 230/2017 – ‘Disposizioni volte a prevenire e gestire l’introduzione e la diffusione delle specie esotiche invasive’ (National strategies to prevent the introduction of invasive species)¹.

If and once pathogens, parasites and non-native species will be detected LIFE NatuReef will report immediately any suspicion or confirmation of the presence of these diseases to the competent authorities. Then, waiting for the measures that should be taken by the competent authorities, the Consortium, will adopt a precautionary approach:

- 1) do not carry on operations that might contribute to further dispersal.
- 2) Carry out risk assessments.
- 3) Seek and follow advice from the relevant authorities. This may include not moving any material.

¹ <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it/it/archivio/notizie-e-novita-normative/notizie-ispra/2018/02/pubblicato-il-nuovo-decreto-legislativo-sulle-specie-invasive-divieti-controlli-eradicazione-e-gestione>

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3 Biosecurity plan during field activities

To prevent t accidental introductions of invasive species and pathogens during field activities four steps will be performed:

- 1) All the equipment, clothing, and boats after carrying out fieldwork activities will be **CHECKED** for fouling material. Before leaving the site all visible hitchhikers, sediment, and debris need to be removed. If this occurs away from the site, ensure that all material is at least disposed of safely, and under no circumstances near a watercourse.
- 2) All fieldwork items will be **CLEANED** thoroughly with freshwater as soon as possible (e.g., fieldwork clothing, restoration equipment, trailer wheels and areas that are damp or hard to reach).
- 3) During cleaning procedures, if needed, a **DISINFECTION** part will be included.
- 4) All the fieldwork items, and equipment such as a trailer and boat need to be **DRIED** in sunlight to drain water from any water remaining before next usage.

4 Biosecurity plan to prevent and monitor oyster diseases and other pathogens

To reduce the likelihood of pathogen introduction and their potential consequences several practices, procedures and policies will be considered. The principal steps in the development of biosecurity strategies are hazard identification, followed by a risk assessment process. Based on this knowledge, risk mitigation (prevention of introduction), disease detection and control (if introduction does take place) and eradication plans can be developed.

Disease from some pathogens is a major threat to native oysters both in aquaculture and in the wild. In particular, the haplosporidian species *Bonamia ostreae*, which causes the disease bonamiosis, is still expanding its range in Europe and can cause up to 90% mortality when it arrives in a population. Similarly, invasive non-native species (NIS) are considered a key threat to biodiversity throughout European waters. Harmful algal blooms of species able to produce biotoxins could also affect biodiversity and biosecurity. Vectors include shipping and recreational boating, but a major cause has been shellfish movements. The presence or introduction of a disease or NIS species may negatively impact the conservation objectives for protected species and habitats. They also pose a threat to the success of native oyster restoration through competition for food and space, predation, outbreaks of diseases, negatively impacting the biodiversity associated with healthy biogenic habitat, and reputational damage. Another relevant aspect of biosecurity is to maintain and verify a high genetic diversity in the seeded populations, which should be achieved by using local wild specimens in the seeding practices and by a good connectivity with other natural populations.

Native oysters are susceptible or may be a vector to a range of other parasites and pathogens. Here there is a non-exhaustive list of known pathogens and parasites affecting the native oyster (zu Ermgassen et al. 2020):

- *Boccardia* (genus of),
- *Cliona celata*,
- *Cliona viridis*,
- *Gyrodinium aureolum*,
- *Haplosporidium armoricatum*,
- *Herrmannella duggani*,
- *Hexamita inflata*,
- *Mytilicola intestinalis*,
- *Nocardia crassostreae*,
- *Ostracoblabe implexa*,
- *Papovaviridae* (family of),
- *Perkinsus mediterraneus*,
- *Polydora* (genus of),
- *Pseudoklossia* (genus of),
- *Vibrio* spp. (e.g. *V. alginolyticus*, *V. anguillarum*, *V. coralliilyticus*, *V. neptunius*, *V. ostreicida*, *V. tubiashi*)

To detect these organisms a monitoring plan is included in the project.

Benthic communities within the Bevano river mouth monitoring area will be characterised. The spatial distribution of sediment features (grain size, organic matter contents) and of the macrobenthic species throughout the study area will be mapped based on a field survey collecting sediment and benthic assemblage samples that will be analysed at the UNIBO laboratories. We will use integrative approaches based on morphological identification and eDNA metabarcoding to evaluate community structure. Specifically, sediment and water samples will be collected and these eDNA samples will be analysed using a multi-marker approach to characterize all the eukaryotic communities (e.g., COI for most metazoans, 18S rDNA for non-metazoans). For each selected marker, a sequencing library will be prepared, and, after purification, the library will be sequenced using a MinION Mk1C sequencing platform. The Oxford Nanopore MinION will allow the generation of low-cost and low-time sequence data in the field. These molecular analyses should allow the detection of the eukaryotic pathogens among the above-listed, if already present in the environment (sediment and water).

5 Biosecurity plan to prevent and monitor non-indigenous species invasion

Before transplanting, individuals will be morphologically analysed to taxonomically classify them and prevent the spreading of invasive competitors: for instance, *Ostrea edulis* (native species) will be selected instead of *Magallana gigas* (invasive species). Furthermore, to prevent proliferation of possible benthic microalgae carryovers of invasive or harmful species, swabs and subsequent morphological identification will be performed (Clementson et al. 2021).

The introduction plan also envisions a genetic screening step to enforce the morphological analyses, using a multi-marker approach, that will allow a better characterisation of the selected sabellariids and oysters species that will be selected for implant on the basal limestone reef (BLR) and prevent the introduction of non-native species.

6 Biosecurity plan for translocation

One of the key points during translocation is to minimise the physical distance between the donor and receiving site.

Local stock may have adaptations suited for survival in the area and existing genetic structure in the population is maintained, ensuring genetic diversity. However, when considering using wild stocks, the impact on the donor site must be considered first. Indeed, the use of wild stocks to supply the demand from restoration has the potential to further damage the remaining populations. In this case, being a first demonstration restoration project in the area, the use of wild stock, already exploited to feed aquaculture plants, represents a good option and the project will ensure that the stock selection process is conducted responsibly and in accordance with legislation and biosecurity protocols. In addition, when needed, oysters will be kept alive in aquaculture facilities at the Ravenna harbour pending sowing on the BLR.

Since the availability of wild oysters cannot always be guaranteed, arrangements will also be made with aquaculture facilities for the supply of certified young oysters, for instance from the oyster farms in Mali Ston Bay in Croatia, which may provide flat oyster spat for the Mediterranean region (see also Deliverable D4.2 - Oyster supply and storing plan).

Concerning sabellariid worm reefs, translocation of individuals will be performed taking small portions of reefs spontaneously developed along the artificial breakwaters already present a few hundred meters to the north (inside the same NATURA 2000 site). Being a highly gregarious species, these portions will represent the growth and diffusion kernels, while the BLR and the oysters will provide adequate protection.

7 Biosecurity plan to ensure and monitor oyster and sabellariid polychaetes population genetic diversity and connectivity

Genomic characterization of the deployed oysters (*Ostrea edulis*) and of the *Sabellaria* individuals from the populations used for the transplant will be performed. Depending on the source oyster populations, 20-30 individuals will be sampled for genetic analysis. Sequence polymorphism of mitochondrial markers and the RADseq library will be carried out following Terzin et al. (2021) and Muir et al. (2020). Populations with higher genetic diversity will be selected for transplant to increase population resilience, avoid inbreeding and ensure its long-term adaptability (e.g., changing environment).

To monitor the changes in genetic diversity of the restored populations and the parentage relationships among individuals every year, several recruits will be sampled (according to the total number of recruits in order not to negatively affect the restoration) and will be analysed with the same markers and SNPs used before.

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